

An Automated Framework for Testing MUOS Voice Calls

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Abstract—The Mobile User Objective System (MUOS) is the next generation UHF satellite communications (SATCOM) system for the Department of Defense (DoD). It consists of four geosynchronous satellites and four ground stations, uses a Spectrally Adaptive Wideband Code Division Multiple Access (SA-WCDMA) waveform, and it will provide worldwide voice and data capabilities for the military. Before it can be used by soldiers in the field, the system must be extensively tested to verify that it works and meets specified requirements. This paper discusses an automated test capability developed to analyze the performance of voice calls made over MUOS. There are two types of voice calls that can be made: point-to-point (which consists of 2 MUOS terminals that can talk to each other) and group (which consists of 2 or more MUOS terminals where terminals talk to all other terminals connected to the group). The automation software can be used to measure performance metrics that include voice quality, latency, call completion rate, service connection time, and various other timing metrics of the two types of voice calls. The software also logs status information from the radios and the radio's measurements of Common Pilot Channel (CPICH) received signal code power (RSCP), CPICH signal-to-interference ratio (SIR), satellite beam carrier (SBC), and bit error rate (BER). The logged information can be used to explain poor performance issues, such as failed calls, long service connection times, etc.

In addition to analyzing the performance of MUOS voice calls, the automation software also has several benefits over human testing. Typically, in order to conduct voice call tests, a human tester has to be assigned to and operate each radio. Especially for group voice calls which can consist of as many as 20 or more radios, it can be very costly to conduct hours of testing. However, the automation software only requires a laptop to be connected to each radio and does not require any human operators; thus significantly reducing costs. Furthermore, the results obtained from automated testing are objective and more precise than those obtained from human testing. The laptops used for automated testing are synchronized using the Network Time Protocol which enables the automation software to achieve timing accuracy on the order of milliseconds, whereas human testing only achieves accuracy on the order of seconds at best.

Keywords—MUOS; automated testing; voice quality

I. INTRODUCTION

The Mobile User Objective System (MUOS) is the next generation UHF satellite communications (SATCOM) system

for the military. It utilizes commercial 3G Spectrally Adaptive Wideband Code Division Multiple Access (SA-WCDMA) technology and applies it to SATCOM [1]. Instead of using cellular radio towers, four geosynchronous satellites are used in both the uplink and downlink. Four ground stations are used to control the satellites and route information between users. When completed, MUOS will provide increased capacity, improved mobile communications, and higher data rates than legacy UHF SATCOM systems [1].

Before MUOS can be used operationally, it must be extensively tested to verify that it meets specified requirements. Human radio operators can be used to verify qualitative requirements and some quantitative requirements as well, however, the obtained results are prone to human error and likely not as precise as what is achievable using computers. Thus an automated test capability was developed to test voice calls over MUOS. Voice call testing is a very time consuming and labor intensive task since it requires radio operators to speak specified phrases numerous times. In order to verify requirements, the operators have to test for multiple hours each day and for multiple days. Automated testing not only reduces costs and human labor, but it also produces more accurate results than human testing which is critical when validating timing requirements.

This paper discusses software that was developed to automate two types of MUOS voice calls: point-to-point and group. In a point-to-point call, two MUOS terminals talk to each other. In a group call, however, two or more MUOS terminals talk to each other. When one radio talks, all of the other radios in the group receive the transmission. Both the point-to-point and group call automation consists of two steps:

- 1) *Running software applications to perform the actual calls using MUOS terminals and writing information to log files.*

- 2) *After all calls have finished, analyzing the logs in post-processing to measure various performance metrics.*

The software applications in the first step were written in Java due to the real-time requirements in controlling MUOS terminals, while the software used in the second step was written in MATLAB because of MATLAB's ease-of-use in handling text files and performing mathematical calculations on large data sets. The MUOS terminals used for testing were the AN/PRC-155 manpack radios.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the design of the point-to-point voice call automation software. Section III discusses the design of the software to automate group voice calls. Section IV discusses experimental findings concerning strictly the automation software and not MUOS (note that since MUOS is a military system, no system nor radio performance results will be given). Lastly, Section V contains concluding remarks.

II. POINT-TO-POINT VOICE CALL AUTOMATION DESIGN

A. Software Automation

The software that automates point-to-point voice calls consists of two software applications: a transmitter application and a receiver application. As shown in Fig. 1, the transmitter application is connected to and controls the radio that initiates voice calls, and the receiver application is connected to and controls the radio that receives incoming voice calls. The transmitter application drives the call process whereas the receiver application aids the transmitter application by feeding back status information. The receiver application communicates with the transmitter application over an Ethernet connection with a client server socket connection, with the transmitter being the server. Both applications control the radios via the Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP). The SNMP4J API is used to handle the SNMP interface [2]. It enables the applications to set and get various radio parameters. It also allows the applications to utilize trap receivers to receive status information from the radios in real-time.

The flow of the transmitter and receiver applications is shown in Fig. 2. Both applications first login to their respective radios and then launch the MUOS waveform. Whenever the receiver radio gets service, the receiver application notifies the transmitter application via Ethernet. Once both radios have service, the transmitter application makes its radio place a point-to-point voice call to the receiver radio and waits a specified amount of time for the call to connect. During this time, the receiver application detects if there is an incoming call on its radio, and if so, attempts to answer the call.

Fig. 1. Setup of point-to-point voice call automation.

Fig. 2. Flow of point-to-point voice call automation software.

If a successful call connection occurs, the transmitter application then plays an audio file containing human speech into the microphone input of the radio. Custom audio cables were developed for the purpose of interfacing a computer's audio input and output jacks to the radio's audio output and input ports. On the receive side, the receiver application records the audio that is heard by the receive radio and writes it to a Waveform Audio File Format (WAV) file for post-analysis. Both the transmitter application and receiver application log the time that they start playing/recording audio to facilitate the latency calculation that is done in post-processing. After the transmitter application finishes playing the audio file, it makes its radio end the call.

After the call ends or if the call connection fails, the transmitter application receives information from the receiver application letting it know if the receive radio received an incoming call and if the call had connected for the receive radio. The transmitter application uses this information to log running sums of the number of successful calls and the number of failed calls. Lastly, the transmitter application waits until the receiver application notifies it that it is ready to receive another call, and the point-to-point voice call process repeats.

B. Metrics Analysis

After the test is stopped, the logs and WAV files produced by the transmitter and receiver applications can be analyzed to calculate the following metrics:

- number of successful calls
- number of failed calls
- latency
- call connection time

- percentage of time with service
- voice quality
- satellite beam carrier (SBC) index [3]
- bit error rate (BER)
- Common Pilot Channel (CPICH) received signal code power (RSCP)
- CPICH signal-to-interference ratio (SIR)

The two most involved calculations are latency and voice quality. To measure latency, as mentioned earlier, the transmitter and receiver applications log the time when they start playing/recording their respective audio files which occurs as soon as the call connects. The audio file played by the transmitter has 1 second of silence at the beginning before the human speech to ensure that the recorded audio file captures all spoken words and to facilitate detecting the beginning of the speech. The receiver application only records audio for a specified time interval and leaves the speech analysis for post-processing. The speech detection algorithm is critical to provide accurate latency measurements. It is common to transmit a sinusoidal signal for a brief period of time to measure latency, but we wanted to simulate human operators using the radios, so we chose to just transmit human speech and rely on a signal detection algorithm to detect the beginning of the speech. In post-processing, a matched filter type of algorithm is used to detect when speech starts. Fig. 3 shows the key times associated with the latency calculation. Both laptops use the Network Time Protocol (NTP) for synchronization, which also facilitates the latency calculation. The transmitter starts playing the audio file when the call connects at time t_1 , while the receiver starts recording audio at time t_2 . Note that t_1 and t_2 ideally should be the same, but typically differ due to computer and operating system performance. Actual human speech starts playing at t_1+1 . The speech appears at the receiver at t_2+d . The speech detection algorithm is used to determine d . The latency is then given by $t_2+d-(t_1+1)$.

Fig. 3. Point-to-point voice call latency.

The methods described in [4] and [5] are used to objectively measure voice quality. Perceptual Evaluation of Speech Quality (PESQ) is a double-ended method in that it uses both the received audio and original transmitted audio to measure the voice quality. It produces a score that can be converted into a Mean Opinion Score (MOS). The P.563 method is a single-ended method that only analyzes the received audio to measure the voice quality. The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) provides fully functional software implementations of both methods, written in ANSI-C, that can be utilized by MATLAB.

III. GROUP VOICE CALL AUTOMATION DESIGN

A. Software Automation

The group voice call automation software has some similarities to the point-to-point voice call automation software, but differs in many ways due to the nature of group calls. The software that automates group voice calls consists of only one software application that supports both transmitting and receiving audio. Since two or more radios (also referred to as nodes) participate in a group call, the group application software is designed to have a distributed structure as opposed to a centralized structure like the client server design of the point-to-point software. The group software uses multicast User Datagram Protocol (UDP) packets to communicate between the laptops. Each node receives status information from every other node and transmits its own status information out to the other nodes.

For N nodes, the group call automation software numbers each node 1 through N , and all N nodes continually attempt to participate in group calls. Each group call consists of a round in which each node sequentially transmits when it is its turn or receives a transmission from another node when it is not its turn. Since the nodes operate in a distributed manner, it is critical that they stay synchronized, which is achieved with the status information that is transmitted between the nodes.

Each node uses the finite-state machines (FSM) shown in Fig. 4 and 5 for their operation. If it is a node's turn to transmit, then it follows the FSM in Fig. 4. If it is supposed to receive, then it follows the FSM in Fig. 5. The labels corresponding to each state are given in Table I. In State 0, a node has service or is waiting to acquire service, but is not connected to the group. A node transitions to State 1 if it successfully connects to the group. It waits in State 1 until all other nodes have also joined the group. If a node fails to join the group, it notifies the other nodes and the other nodes proceed to perform a round without the failed node. Once all nodes have joined (or failed to join) the group, Node 1 (or the next largest node in the event Node 1 failed to join the group) is designated as the transmitter and follows the FSM in Fig. 4. The other nodes are designated as receivers and follow the FSM in Fig. 5. In State 2, the transmitter plays an audio file containing human speech into the microphone input of the radio and the receivers record the audio that is heard by their radios and write it to a WAV file for post-analysis. This is just like the point-to-point voice call, except instead of just one WAV file per transmission, there are now $N-1$ WAV files per transmission, assuming all N nodes are joined to the group. When the transmitter node attempts to

play the audio file, it receives status information from its radio notifying it if the radio actually sent out a transmission or not. If it did send out a transmission, then the node moves to State 3 and notifies the other nodes that a transmission was actually sent out. If it did not send out a transmission, then the node instead moves to State 4 and notifies the other nodes that a transmission never occurred. States 3 and 4 help simplify the missed call analysis for group calls. From States 3 or 4, the transmit node either returns to State 1 and becomes a receiver or ends the round by going to State 5 if it is the largest valued node in the round. When the round ends, all nodes in the round disconnect from the group call and return to State 0.

B. Metrics Analysis

The metrics that are calculated are the same as the ones from the point-to-point voice call analysis, except that in addition, the number of successful and failed group transmissions can also be calculated. This calculation can be used to identify if a particular radio experienced issues, such as if other radios rarely heard its transmissions or if it rarely heard transmissions from other radios.

Fig. 4. State transition diagram of FSM for transmitting node in group call.

Fig. 5. State transition diagram of FSM for receiving nodes in group call.

TABLE I. FSM STATES FOR FIG. 4 AND 5

State #	State if Transmitter Node (Fig. 4)	State if Receiver Node (Fig. 5)
0	idle	idle
1	connected to group	connected to group
2	play audio	record audio
3	TX success	
4	TX fail	
5	end round	

IV. DISCUSSION

Since MUOS is a military system, experimental results will not be presented. However, a couple of findings strictly about the automation software with MUOS radios excluded will be discussed. For these results, the MUOS radios were removed from the setup shown in Fig. 1 and an audio cable connected the speaker output of a laptop running the point-to-point transmitter application directly to the microphone input of a laptop running the point-to-point receiver application. Both laptops were Dell Latitude D630 laptops running Microsoft Windows XP Service Pack 3. In order to test the latency and voice quality inherent in the laptops, the transmitter application continually transmitted a sentence of speech and the receiver application continually recorded the audio, exactly like the actual point-to-point voice software operates except that the applications used the beginning of every minute as a trigger instead of being notified that a call connected. The audio files were processed exactly the same way in post-processing as they normally would be when analyzing radio recordings.

The clock offset between the two laptops is shown in Fig. 6. As seen in the figure, the clock offset between the two laptops running NTP is relatively small, especially after the first few minutes. The average offset is $-2.3 \mu\text{s}$ with $\sigma = 0.2 \text{ ms}$. Note that a negative offset means that the clock of the laptop running the receiver application is actually ahead of the clock of the other laptop.

The latency measurement between the laptops is shown in Fig. 7. A total of 988 measurements were taken. The figure shows that the latency inherent in the laptops does not fluctuate significantly. The average latency is 110.419 ms and $\sigma = 1.919 \text{ ms}$. By using this measurement, when latency is measured with MUOS radios as part of the test configuration, this number can be subtracted from the latency measurements and what remains can be attributed to the MUOS system.

Fig. 6. Clock offset between laptops using NTP.

Voice quality measurements were also performed on the 988 recorded audio files. The results are given in Table II. Note that the mapping of MOS values to qualitative scores is: 5 - excellent, 4 - good, 3 - fair, 2 - poor, 1 - bad [6]. Since there was only a short audio cable running between the two laptops, one would expect little (if any) distortion in the speech, which is in agreement with the MOS values given by the P.563 method. However, the PESQ average MOS of 2.822 corresponds to fair voice quality, which does not agree with the test configuration. In actual testing, this discrepancy has also been observed. The P.563 method seems to provide MOS values that agree well with subjective human voice quality testing, while PESQ almost always gives a poor assessment that does not agree with human results. It should be noted that for the P.563 method to work, we found that it requires only the speech to be contained in the audio file passed to it. It does not work well if silence precedes the speech, thus making the speech detection algorithm used very important.

Fig. 7. Measurements of latency inherent in laptops.

TABLE II. VOICE QUALITY MEASUREMENTS WITHOUT MUOS RADIOS

	MOS	
	PESQ	P.563
Mean	2.822	4.256
Standard Deviation	0.225	0.129

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an automated voice testing capability for MUOS was presented. The design differences in the software for point-to-point calls vs. group calls were discussed. The automation software is currently being used to analyze the performance of MUOS terminals and verify the system satisfies requirements.

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